

DEVELOPMENT OF INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RETARDATION AND DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN

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Annotation: Assessment of electrocardiographic and echocardiographic parameters in infants born at term with mild IUGR.

Children were examined on days 2–3 (n = 164), 1 (n = 154), 3 (n = 142), 6 (n = 133), and 12 (n = 130) months of life. No medical intervention was performed. The duration of the study is 3 years. Clinical, laboratory and instrumental (electrocardiography and echocardiography) examination were performed. Heart rate, frequency of early ventricular repolarization syndrome and nonspecific disorders of the repolarization process were assessed; in standard lead II, the morphology, amplitude in millimeters and width in seconds of the P wave; duration in seconds of the PQ interval (PR), QRS complex and QT interval; morphology, amplitude in millimeters of the T wave, as well as the thickness of the interventricular septum and the posterior wall of the left ventricle. Nonparametric methods of statistical analysis were used. Some electrocardiographic and echocardiographic features were identified in the dynamics of growth and development of the body of infants born at term with mild IUGR, indicating a high frequency of changes in the cardiovascular system, requiring corrective measures.

Relevance. The search from the neonatal period of growth and development of an individual for early changes in the cardiovascular system in infants born with intrauterine growth and development retardation (IUGR), identified using routine examination methods, determined the relevance of the study. a technique for recording and studying electric fields generated during the work of the heart.

Electrocardiography is a relatively inexpensive but valuable method of electrophysiological instrumental diagnostics in cardiology.

The direct result of electrocardiography is an electrocardiogram (ECG). Key features to evaluate on an ECG include the cardiac axis, frequency and regularity of the waves, and the intervals and amplitude of each beat (eg, P wave, PQ interval, QRS complex, ST segment)

Echocardiography (Greek ἠχώ - echo, echo + καρδία - heart + γράφω - write, depict) is an ultrasound method aimed at studying the morphological and functional changes of the heart and its valve apparatus. It is based on capturing ultrasound signals reflected from the structures of the heart.

Purpose of the study. Assessment of electrocardiographic and echocardiographic parameters in infants born at term with mild IUGR.

Patients and methods. Children were examined on days 2–3 (n = 164), 1 (n = 154), 3 (n = 142), 6 (n = 133), and 12 (n = 130) months of life. No medical intervention was performed. The duration of the study is 3 years. Clinical, laboratory and instrumental (electrocardiography and echocardiography) examination were performed. Heart rate, frequency of early ventricular repolarization syndrome and nonspecific disorders of the repolarization process were assessed; in standard lead II, the morphology, amplitude in millimeters and width in seconds of the P wave; duration in seconds of the PQ interval (PR), QRS complex and QT interval; morphology, amplitude in millimeters of the T wave, as well as the thickness of the interventricular septum and the posterior wall of the left ventricle. Nonparametric methods of statistical analysis were used.

Results. The median amplitude of the P wave on days 2–3 in children of subgroup 1b compared with children of group 3 is 0.2 mm less; at 1 month in children of the 1st (1b) group compared to children of the 3rd group it is 0.1 mm less; at 3 months in children of subgroup 1a, compared with children of subgroup 1b, it is 0.35 mm less, in children of subgroup 1b, compared with children of group 3, it is 0.2 mm more; at 6 months, children of the 1st (1a and 1b) group compared to

children of the 3rd group had an increase of 0.2 mm; at 12 months in children of subgroup 1a, compared with children of subgroup 1b, it is 0.2 mm less, in children of subgroup 1b, compared with children of group 2, it is 0.2 mm more, in children of group 1 (1a), compared with children of the 3rd group it is less by 0.2 (0.5) mm, and in comparison with children of the 3rd group it is less by 0.2 mm. From 3 to 6 months it increased by 0.35 mm in children of subgroup 1a. In children of the 1st (1a) group, a slowdown from 2–3 days to 1 month of intra-atrial conduction by 0.01 s, from 1 to 3 months of intraventricular conduction by 0.01 s, from 3 to 6 months of intra-atrial conduction by 0.01 s. With. Electrical systole in children of group 1 slowed down from 1 to 3 and from 3 to 6 months by 0.01 s; in children of subgroup 1a from 1 to 3 months it increased by 0.01 s, from 3 to 6 months it decreased by 0.01 s, from 6 to 12 months it increased by 0.01 s. The median amplitude of the T wave on days 2–3, at 1 month in children of the 1st (1a and 1b) group compared to children of the 3rd group is greater by 0.4 mm and 0.3 mm, respectively; at 3 months in children of subgroup 1a, compared with children of subgroup 1b, it is 0.35 mm less, and compared with children of group 2, it is 0.2 mm less, in children of subgroup 1b, compared with children of group 2, it is more by 0.15 mm, in children of the 1st (1b) group compared to children of the 3rd group it is 0.3 (0.45) mm more; at 12 months, children of subgroup 1b compared with children of group 2 were 0.4 mm larger, and children of group 1 (1a) were 0.3 mm smaller than children of group 3. From 2–3 days to 1 month in children of the 1st (1a) group it increased by 0.8 mm. In children of subgroup 1b at the age of 2–5 days, the VSD was minimal (3.6 mm), by 6 months there was greater thickening of it (by 1.1 mm) and of the posterior wall of the left ventricle (by 1.0 mm). At 6 months, compared to children of the 3rd group, they had a larger VSD (4.7 mm). At 12 months, these children had a larger VSD (5 mm) compared to children of subgroup 1a. At 6 months, children of subgroup 1a had less LVAD (4.3 mm) compared to children of subgroup 1b. At 12 months, children of subgroup 1a, compared with children of group 2, subgroup 1b, had smaller VSDs (4.8 mm).

Conclusion. Some electrocardiographic and echocardiographic features were identified in the dynamics of growth and development of the body of infants born at term with mild IUGR, indicating a high frequency of changes in the cardiovascular system, requiring corrective measures.

Literature:

1. bdurasulovich Y. S., Rafikovna K. L. BOLALARDA UCHRAYDIGAN UROLITIAZ KASALLIGINI EPIDEMIOLOGIYASI VA XAVF OMILLARI (Adabiyotlar sharhi) //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 1.
2. Юсупов Ш. А., Хакимова Л. Р. ПРОГНОСТИЧЕСКАЯ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЬ ИММУНОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ МОЧЕКАМЕННОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ У ДЕТЕЙ //Вестник Авиценны. – 2023. – Т. 25. – №. 3. – С. 346-355.
3. Хакимова Л. Р. и др. ИЗУЧЕНИЕ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ АУТОШТАММОВ LACTOBACILLUS SPP. ДЛЯ СОЗДАНИЯ ПРОБИОТИКОВ //КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ЛАБОРАТОРНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА. – 2023. – Т. 68. – №. 8.
4. Гимранова И. А. и др. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПАРОДОНТА: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ) //КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ЛАБОРАТОРНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА. – 2023. – Т. 68. – №. 9.
5. Abdurasulovich Y. S., Rafikovna K. L. CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF CALCULOUS PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILDHOOD DEPENDING ON AGE GROUPS //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 2.
6. Хакимова Л., Лапасова М., Лапасова З. The use of innovative learning methods in high educational establishments as a stage of implementation of improving the quality of the educational process //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1/S. – С. 121-125.

7. Юсупов Ш. А., Хакимова Л. Р. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ НА СЛУЖБЕ КАЧЕСТВЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ МЕДИЦИНЫ //Актуальные вопросы современного медицинского образования: совершенствование подготовки медицинских кадров. – 2022. – С. 63-65.
8. Хакимова Л. Р. Развитие образности речи детей старшего дошкольного возраста при обучении художественному описанию природы //ДЕТСКИЙ САД, ШКОЛА, ВУЗ: ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОПРОВОЖДЕНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ. – 2022. – С. 457-460.
9. Akbarovna K. S. et al. REVIEW OF THE COURSE AND TREATMENT FEATURES OF COVID-19 PATIENTS WITH CONCOMITANT CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE //Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 2.
10. Khakimova L. et al. Acne in Allergic Skin Diseases //Texas Journal of Medical Science. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 129-131.
11. Rafikovna K. L., Abdurasulovich Y. S. ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF GENETIC FACTORS ON THE INCIDENCE OF UROLITHIASIS IN THE CHILDHOOD POPULATION (Literature review) //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 2.
12. Юлдашова Н., Хакимова Л. РОЛЬ СЕМЕЙНОЙ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ СЕСТРЫ В РАБОТЕ «ШКОЛЫ МАТЕРИНСТВА» //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 507.
13. Хакимова Л., Лапасова М. Ўспирин-қиз болалар ва уларнинг оналарининг репродуктив саломатлик ҳақидаги билимларини текшириш натижаларининг таҳлили ва унинг сифат кўрсаткичини яхшилаш //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1/3. – С. 138-144.
14. Хусинова Ш. А., Хакимова Л. Р., Курбанов Б. В. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОЦЕНКИ КАЧЕСТВА ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С СЕРДЕЧНОЙ

НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬЮ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПОЛИКЛИНИКИ //Journal of cardiorespiratory research. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 82-84.

15. Хакимова Л. и др. Безопасное материнство и эффективный антенатальный уход //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8/S. – С. 91-95.
16. Хакимова Л., Лапасова М. Анализ результатов тестирования знаний девочек-подростков и их матерей о репродуктивном здоровье и повышение качества оказания медицинских услуг //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1/S. – С. 138-144.
17. Хакимова Л., Лапасов С. Birlamchi tibbiyot sanitariya yordami muassasalarida belda og ‘riq sindromi bilan bemorlarni integratsiya usulida olib borish //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/s. – С. 558-564.
18. Хакимова Л., Лапасов С. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ ПНЕВМОНИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА //InterConf. – 2020.
19. Хакимова Л., Лапасова Ф. Роль дистанционного обучения в системе высшего образования в период карантинных мероприятий в связи с пандемией Covid–19 //InterConf. – 2020.
20. Хусинова Ш., Аблакулова М., Хакимова Л. Процесс рационального назначения лекарственных средств и выбор персонального лекарства в практике ВОП //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 683-689.